

Influence of Librarians Knowledge and Readiness towards Acceptance of Metadata Mapping and Aggregation for Information Retrieval in Federal Universities, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: This study examines the influence of librarians' knowledge on their readiness and acceptance of metadata mapping and aggregation for information retrieval in federal universities in Nigeria. Metadata mapping and aggregation are essential for efficient information retrieval, yet their adoption in Nigerian universities remains limited.

Method: A quantitative approach with a survey research design was employed. Data were collected using a questionnaire distributed to 440 respondents, with 402 questionnaires returned and deemed usable for analysis (response rate: 91.4%). Descriptive statistics were used to analyze awareness, readiness, and acceptance levels, while inferential statistics established relationships between variables.

Findings/Results: The findings revealed that librarians had moderate awareness of metadata mapping practices. Readiness to adopt these practices was high in terms of training ($M > 2.50$), moderate in terms of infrastructure, and low in terms of competencies. Acceptance of metadata mapping and aggregation practices was high. A statistically significant relationship was found between librarians' knowledge of metadata mapping and aggregation and their readiness to adopt these practices ($p < 0.05$).

Implications: The results indicate that librarians' knowledge significantly influences their readiness and acceptance of metadata mapping and aggregation, suggesting that improved knowledge and skills could enhance information retrieval systems in Nigerian universities. However, limitations in infrastructure and competencies highlight areas needing attention.

Conclusion: The study concludes that librarians' knowledge is a critical determinant of their readiness and acceptance of metadata mapping and aggregation practices, and enhancing this knowledge is essential for improving information retrieval in federal universities in Nigeria.

Recommendations: The study recommends that universities organize targeted training programs on metadata standards, tools, and best practices. Librarians should be encouraged to pursue certifications and continuing education in metadata management. Library science programs in Nigerian universities should include comprehensive courses on metadata management, digital cataloguing, and information retrieval systems. Universities should establish forums for librarians to share best practices, challenges, and solutions related to metadata management, and practical sessions on metadata tools should be integrated into curricula to enhance future librarians' proficiency.

Keywords: Librarians' Knowledge, Readiness, Acceptance, mapping, Aggregation, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Information retrieval (IR) is the process of obtaining relevant information from large collections of data, typically through digital systems such as online catalogs, databases, and digital repositories. In academic libraries, IR systems are critical for enabling users to locate resources efficiently, supporting research, teaching, and learning. These systems rely on structured metadata to organize and retrieve information, ensuring that users can access materials like books, journals, and digital content with precision and speed. The effectiveness of IR depends on the quality of metadata, the design of retrieval systems, and the ability of librarians to leverage these tools to meet user needs. As information environments grow increasingly complex, the role of advanced techniques like metadata mapping and aggregation has become essential in enhancing IR performance (Chowdhury, 2019).

The evolution of IR has been driven by technological advancements, including the development of integrated library systems and web-based platforms. However, challenges such as inconsistent metadata standards, limited interoperability between systems, and the growing volume of digital content complicate IR processes. In academic libraries, particularly in developing regions like Sub-Saharan Africa, resource constraints and varying levels of technological infrastructure compound these challenges. Effective IR requires not only robust systems but also knowledgeable librarians who can navigate and optimize these tools to deliver seamless access to information (Asogwa & Ugwu, 2021).

Librarians' knowledge is foundational to the success of IR systems, as they are responsible for designing, managing, and maintaining the metadata frameworks that underpin these systems. This knowledge encompasses understanding metadata schemas (e.g., Dublin Core, MARC), cataloging principles, and the application of controlled vocabularies to ensure consistency in resource description. In the digital era, librarians must also be proficient in using library management systems and emerging technologies like linked data and semantic web tools to enhance IR. Studies indicate that librarians with strong technical knowledge can significantly improve the discoverability of resources, thereby enhancing user satisfaction (Ocholla & Mutula, 2020).

However, gaps in librarians' knowledge, particularly in advanced metadata management techniques, remain a concern. In many developing countries, including Nigeria, librarians often lack adequate training in modern IR technologies due to limited access to professional development opportunities and outdated curricula in library schools. This knowledge gap can hinder the adoption of innovative practices like metadata mapping and aggregation, which are critical for integrating disparate data sources and improving retrieval accuracy. Continuous professional development and exposure to global standards are essential to equip librarians with the skills needed to manage complex IR systems effectively (Igwe & Oyewo, 2022).

Librarians' readiness refers to their preparedness to adopt and implement new technologies and practices in their workflows. Metadata mapping involves aligning metadata elements from different schemas to enable interoperability, while aggregation consolidates metadata from multiple sources to create unified access points for users. These processes are vital for improving IR in digital libraries by ensuring seamless integration of resources across platforms. Readiness encompasses technical skills, access to infrastructure, and a willingness to embrace change.

Research suggests that librarians who are trained in metadata standards and have access to supportive technologies are more likely to adopt these practices effectively (Lampert & Vaughan, 2021).

Despite the importance of readiness, many librarians face barriers such as inadequate technological infrastructure, limited funding, and resistance to change due to entrenched traditional practices. In African academic libraries, readiness is further challenged by unreliable internet connectivity and insufficient institutional support for technology adoption. A study by Adeyemi and Oluwabiyi (2023) found that while some librarians are aware of metadata mapping and aggregation, their readiness is often limited by a lack of hands-on training and institutional policies that prioritize these technologies. Addressing these barriers requires targeted interventions, including capacity-building programs and infrastructure investments.

Acceptance of metadata mapping and aggregation refers to librarians' willingness to integrate these techniques into their professional practice. Acceptance is influenced by factors such as perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and organizational support, as outlined in the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989). When librarians perceive metadata mapping and aggregation as tools that enhance IR efficiency and user satisfaction, they are more likely to adopt them. Successful acceptance also depends on a supportive institutional environment, including access to training, reliable technology, and leadership that encourages innovation (Hossain & Rahman, 2022).

However, resistance to change, particularly among librarians accustomed to traditional cataloguing methods can hinder acceptance. In resource-constrained settings, acceptance is further complicated by practical challenges such as limited access to advanced software and insufficient time to learn new systems. A study by Okoroma (2021) on Nigerian academic libraries found that while librarians recognize the potential of metadata mapping and aggregation, their acceptance is often tempered by concerns about complexity and lack of institutional support. Fostering acceptance requires addressing these concerns through user-friendly tools, clear communication of benefits, and institutional incentives.

Librarians' knowledge and readiness for metadata mapping and aggregation highlights both opportunities and challenges in enhancing IR. Metadata mapping, which involves aligning metadata elements across different schemas, is critical for ensuring interoperability between systems. For instance, mapping Dublin Core elements to MARC records enables libraries to integrate local catalogs with global repositories, improving resource discoverability (Tedd & Butters, 2020). Aggregation, on the other hand, consolidates metadata from multiple sources into a single access point, such as a digital library portal, streamlining IR for users. Studies show that libraries adopting these techniques report higher user satisfaction due to improved access to diverse resources (Choi & Rasmussen, 2021).

Librarians' knowledge of metadata standards is a key determinant of successful IR. Research by Ocholla and Mutula (2020) emphasizes that proficiency in standards like Dublin Core, MODS, and RDF is essential for managing modern IR systems. However, in many African libraries, librarians lack exposure to these standards due to limited training opportunities. A study by Igwe and Oyewo (2022) found that only 30% of librarians in Nigerian university libraries had formal

training in metadata management, highlighting a significant knowledge gap. This gap is particularly pronounced in regions with limited access to continuing education, where librarians rely on outdated cataloging practices.

Readiness for metadata mapping and aggregation is closely tied to technological infrastructure and institutional support. Adeyemi and Oluwabiyi (2023) found that librarians in Nigerian academic libraries are aware of the benefits of these techniques but lack the tools and training to implement them effectively. For example, the absence of reliable internet connectivity and modern library management systems hinders readiness in many institutions. Similarly, a study by Asogwa and Ugwu (2021) noted that libraries with robust ICT infrastructure and regular staff training programs demonstrate higher readiness for adopting advanced metadata practices, underscoring the importance of institutional investment.

Acceptance of metadata mapping and aggregation is influenced by both individual and organizational factors. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) has been widely used to study librarians' adoption of new technologies. Hossain and Rahman (2022) applied TAM to explore librarians' acceptance of metadata tools, finding that perceived usefulness and ease of use significantly predict adoption rates. However, resistance to change remains a barrier, particularly in libraries with hierarchical structures that prioritize traditional practices. Okoroma (2021) reported that Nigerian librarians often view metadata mapping as complex, requiring significant time and effort to master, which reduces acceptance. Providing user-friendly tools and demonstrating tangible benefits can mitigate this resistance.

The finding also highlights regional disparities in the adoption of metadata mapping and aggregation. In developed countries, libraries have widely adopted linked data and semantic web technologies to enhance IR, as evidenced by initiatives like the Library of Congress's BIBFRAME project (Lampert & Vaughan, 2021). In contrast, African libraries lag due to resource constraints and limited exposure to global standards. A study by Nwosu and Eze (2022) found that only 15% of Nigerian academic libraries use advanced metadata aggregation tools, citing funding shortages and lack of expertise as primary barriers. These findings suggest a need for context-specific strategies to promote adoption in resource-scarce settings.

Research gaps remain in understanding the interplay between librarians' knowledge, readiness, and acceptance of metadata mapping and aggregation, particularly in developing countries. While studies have explored these factors individually, there is limited research on how they collectively influence IR outcomes. Additionally, user perspectives on the impact of these techniques on retrieval efficiency are underexplored. The unique challenges of regions like northern Nigeria, including socio-economic constraints and security issues, further necessitate localized studies to identify effective strategies for enhancing librarians' capacity to adopt metadata practices. Against this background, this study investigated the influence of Librarians' Knowledge and Readiness towards Acceptance of Metadata Mapping and Aggregation for Information Retrieval in Federal Universities, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study aims at providing answers to the following research questions:

What is the level of knowledge of metadata mapping and aggregation practices among librarians in Nigerian federal universities?

1. What is the librarians' level of readiness on the adoption of metadata mapping and aggregation practices for information retrieval in terms of training, Infrastructure and competencies?
2. What is the librarians' acceptance of metadata mapping and aggregation practices?
3. What is the relationship between
 - a) the librarians' knowledge of metadata mapping and aggregation practices and the extent to which they accept metadata mapping and aggregation practices in their libraries
 - b) the librarian's knowledge level of metadata mapping and aggregation practices and their readiness level to adopt metadata mapping and aggregation

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a quantitative approach using a survey research design. A questionnaire was distributed to collect data from respondents. 440 copies of questionnaires were administered, with 402 returned and deemed usable for analysis. A cumulative mean score was used for the descriptive analysis of the research questions. For inferential analysis, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used for calculating the relationship between the variables. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient is the single most common type of correlation, which measures the degree of relationship between two continuous variables. The decision of the researcher is to use the p-value of 0.05 as level of significance for testing the hypothesis. The rule is to reject the null hypothesis where the calculated p-value is less than the pre-defined threshold value, otherwise accept it.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1: Response Rate

Response Rate	Frequency	Percentages
Administered	440	100%
Returned	402	91.3%
Not Returned	38	8.7%

440 copies of questionnaire were administered but only 402 copies were returned, cross-checked and found usable for analysis. Fincham (2008) recommended that response rates approximating 60% or more should be the expectation of researchers. Similarly, the Office of Institutional Research, Fairfield University recommended that the average and reasonably acceptable response rate is 60% and not anything below 40% is reasonably acceptable. Mugenda and Mugenda (1999) stated that a response rate of 50% is adequate for analysis, reporting, a response rate of 60% is good, and response rate of 70% and over is excellent. Therefore, the response rate of the current

study which is up to 91.3% is considered reliable for the analysis. Thus, the analysis was done based on 402 copies of questionnaire which were found usable for the analysis.

Librarians' Knowledge of Metadata mapping and Aggregation Practices

Table 2: Librarians' Knowledge level of Metadata Mapping Practices

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Std.
1	I have knowledge on the existence of different types of metadata schemas	10(2.5%)	152(37.8%)	190(47.3%)	50(12.4%)	2.30	.715
2	I have deep knowledge on how metadata records preserve the usefulness of data	12(3.0%)	117(2.1%)	217(54.0%)	56(13.9%)	2.21	.712
3	I am aware that metadata mapping greatly minimizes duplication of efforts	113(28.1%)	216(53.7%)	47(11.7%)	26(6.5%)	3.03	.811
4	I have knowledge on how metadata mapping support local data asset management	25(6.2%)	226(56.2%)	100(24.9%)	51(12.7%)	2.56	.791
5	I have knowledge on how metadata mapping makes it possible to search, retrieve and evaluate data	55(13.7%)	222(55.2%)	85(21.1%)	40(10.0%)	2.73	.820
6	I am aware that metadata brings similar resources together	50(12.4%)	169(42.0%)	121(30.1%)	62(15.4%)	2.51	.899
7	I have knowledge on how to associate metadata elements in one	61(15.2%)	128(31.8%)	105(26.1%)	108(26.9%)	2.35	1.035

schema to the
 equivalent
 elements in
 another schema

Based on the overall findings, table 4.2 reveals that the calculated mean scores of four of the seven items tested under the librarians' knowledge of metadata mapping practices are greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50. However, three of the items had low mean scores of (M=2.30), (M=2.21), and (M=2.35) were below the criterion mean of 2.50 respectively. On the whole, the weighted mean score of 2.52 was greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This implies that the respondents were aware of the concepts of metadata mapping practices. This corroborates the submission of Oguntayo and Adeleke (2016) who revealed that more than half of academic librarians in Nigeria were aware of basic technicalities of metadata. This finding implies that librarians have willingness to complement with the submission of Gbaje (2015) who viewed that awareness about metadata will help librarians and information professionals contribute to the success of the digitization process.

Table 3: Librarians' Knowledge level of Metadata Aggregation Practices

Statements	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Std.
I have knowledge of metadata aggregation as a process where metadata records from different sources and in different formats are aggregated into one common formats	71(17.7%)	123(30.6%)	148(36.8%)	60(14.9%)	2.30	.715
I have knowledge that metadata aggregation provides standardized description of information resources	64(15.9%)	172(42.8%)	93(23.1%)	73(18.2%)	2.51	.951
I have knowledge that metadata aggregation supports local data asset management	91(22.6%)	115(28.6%)	115(28.6%)	81(20.1%)	2.56	.964
Metadata aggregation is often used in the context of webpages to describe page content for a search engine	61(15.2%)	162(40.3%)	105(26.1%)	74(18.4%)	2.54	1.052
I have knowledge that metadata aggregation aids users in finding resources, discover where and by whom it was created	74(18.4%)	137(34.1%)	141(35.1%)	50(12.4%)	2.52	.961

I am aware that metadata aggregation is an amplification of traditional bibliographic practices in an electronic environment .	89(22.1%)	114(28.4%)	112(27.9%)	87(21.6%)	2.58	.928
I have knowledge of how to mitigate the risks involved in the adoption of metadata aggregation	38(9.5%)	123(30.6%)	137(34.1%)	104(25.9%)	2.51	1.062
I have knowledge on the skills required to adopt metadata aggregation in a library	86(21.4%)	105(26.1%)	129(32.1%)	82(20.4%)	2.24	.943

Table 3 reveals that the calculated mean scores of six of the eight items tested under the extent of librarians' knowledge level on metadata aggregation practices are greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50. However, two of the items had low mean scores of (M=2.24), and (M=2.49) were below the criterion mean of 2.50 respectively. Overall, the weighted mean score of 2.47 was less than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This implies that the extent to which the respondents were aware of the concepts of metadata aggregation practices was moderate. This finding indicate that librarians in Nigeria are beginning to comply with the suggestion of Dodiya (2018) in Gujarat University that library science students need awareness of metadata practices, because if they are aware they can provide better services to their users in their professional life. The finding also coincide with the findings of Ottong, Etim, Ukpanah, Umoh, and Enidiok, (2015), who revealed that librarians in University of Uyo, Nigeria were aware of the importance of subject metadata and that subject access is being provided to electronic resources.

Table 4: your readiness towards metadata mapping and aggregation activities in your library

Librarians' Readiness (Training)	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Std.
I am ready to accept training on digital assets management	70(17.4%)	140(34.8%)	132(32.8%)	60(14.9%)	2.49	1.043
I am ready to accept training on MARC cataloguing	85(21.1%)	135(33.6%)	123(30.6%)	59(14.7%)	2.55	.947
I am ready to accept training on a variety of MARC and non-MARC metadata standards and schema	76(18.9%)	154(38.3%)	112(27.9%)	60(14.9%)	2.61	.978
I am ready to accept training on script languages for data manipulation	82(20.4%)	183(45.5%)	98(24.4%)	39(9.7%)	2.61	.957
I am ready to accept training on control vocabularies , authority controls and ontologies	62(15.4%)	203(50.5%)	78(19.4%)	59(14.7%)	2.77	.885
I am ready to accept training on metadata application guidelines	85(21.1%)	182(45.3%)	88(21.9%)	47(11.7%)	2.67	.909

I am ready to accept training on how to work effectively in a diverse team environment or individually	88(21.9%)	159(39.6%)	91(22.6%)	64(15.9%)	2.67	.989
I am ready to accept training on collection development and knowledge organization	78(19.4%)	136(33.8%)	121(30.1%)	67(16.7%)	2.56	.985
Librarians' Readiness (Competencies)						
I have specialized skills in web development, database design and management	30(7.5%)	143(35.6%)	174(43.3%)	55(13.7%)	2.37	.811
I have specialized skills of converting prints to digital or web ready formats	50(12.4%)	119(29.6%)	181(45.0%)	52(12.9%)	2.42	.867
I have specialized skills of creating, converting, organizing and disseminating information in a digital environment	82(20.4%)	151(37.6%)	111(27.6%)	58(14.4%)	2.64	.964
I have good knowledge of scanning skills	35(8.7%)	186(46.3%)	131(32.6%)	50(12.4%)	2.51	.821
I have specialized document analysis skills	60(14.9%)	156(38.8%)	123(30.6%)	63(15.7%)	2.53	.929
I have good knowledge of archival skills required for metadata mapping and aggregation.	49(12.2%)	143(35.6%)	108(26.9%)	102(25.4%)	2.35	.990
Infrastructure						
I am prepared to adopt technological changes in the delivery of library information retrieval services	77(19.2%)	137(34.1%)	97(24.1%)	91(22.6%)	2.50	1.043
I have access to mapping/aggregation infrastructures in my institution	65(16.2%)	115(28.6%)	163(40.5%)	59(14.7%)	2.46	.931
I am ready to monitor the progress in the standard achievement of mapping/aggregation infrastructures	48(11.9%)	148(36.8%)	148(36.8%)	58(14.4%)	2.46	.882

Table 4 shows the mean and standard deviation scores on the Readiness of Academic Librarians towards metadata mapping and aggregation practices which revealed that, the calculated mean scores of all the eight items tested under training parametre are greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50. In addition, the overall weighted mean score of 2.65 was greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This implies that the extent to which the respondents were ready in terms of training is high. This finding indicate that librarians in Nigeria attempt to comply with the suggestion of Akande and Belle (2014) who attested that it is important for organizations to attain a high level of readiness before adopting a technology and lack of readiness before adoption may lead to implementation failure. Therefore, it becomes important for libraries to attain a high level of readiness before adopting metadata mapping and aggregation.

Table 4 shows the mean and standard deviation scores on the Readiness of Academic Librarians towards metadata mapping and aggregation practices in terms of competences revealed that, the calculated mean scores of three of the six items tested under competencies parametre are greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50. However, three of the items tested had low mean scores of

(M=2.37), (M=2.42), and (M=2.35) and were below the criterion mean of 2.50 respectively. In addition, the overall weighted mean score of 2.47 was less than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This implies that the extent to which the respondents were ready in terms of competences is low. As a response to that, Olumide (2014) warned that many organisations that adopt technologies without considering their level of readiness for that technology and this leads to weak implementation and sometimes failure.

Based on the overall findings, table 4 reveals that the calculated mean scores of one of the three items tested under the extent of librarians' readiness on metadata mapping and aggregation in terms of infrastructure is greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50. However, two of the items had low mean scores of (M=2.46), and (M=2.46) were below the criterion mean of 2.50 respectively. Overall, the weighted mean score of 2.47 was less than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This implies that the extent to which the respondents were ready to adopt metadata mapping and aggregation practices in terms of infrastructure was moderate. This needs urgent attention because, readiness according to Olumide (2014) is a phase before adoption and it is an essential factor in determining the success of adoption because lack of readiness has been found to account for majority of the failures in technology adoption.

Table 5: Acceptance of Librarians towards adopting Metadata Mapping and Aggregation in Federal University Libraries

SN	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Std.
	4	3	2	1		
1.						
2.	149(37.1%)	104(25.9%)	91(22.6%)	58(14.4%)	2.86	1.075
3.	117(29.1%)	166(41.3%)	76(18.9%)	43(10.7%)	2.89	.947
4.	161(40.0%)	117(29.1%)	62(15.4%)	62(15.4%)	2.94	1.082
5.	132(32.8%)	130(32.3%)	90(22.4%)	50(12.4%)	2.86	1.016
6.						
7.	141(35.1%)	132(32.8%)	71(17.7%)	58(14.4%)	2.89	1.046
8.	136(33.8%)	117(29.1%)	93(23.1%)	56(13.9%)	2.83	1.049
9.	115(28.6%)	136(33.8%)	110(27.4%)	41(10.2%)	2.81	.966

10.	The use of metadata standards in my job is very useful.	129(32.1%)	113(28.1%)	119(29.6%)	41(10.2%)	2.82	.998
11.	Use intention						
12.	I will like to coordinate with the library management to enhance Metadata Mapping and Aggregation activities in our library	126(31.3%)	113(28.1%)	90(22.4%)	73(18.2%)	2.73	1.092
13.	We have a dedicated personnel for Metadata Mapping and Aggregation activities	103(25.6%)	131(32.6%)	97(24.1%)	71(17.7%)	2.66	1.045
14.	Decision maker						
15.	I see myself as someone who takes decisions when it comes to adopting or implementing new ICT principles.	117(29.1%)	131(32.6%)	109(27.1%)	45(11.2%)	2.80	.985

Based on the overall findings, table 5 reveals that the calculated mean scores of all the four items tested under Perceived Ease of Use construct are greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50 under 4-point likert scale. However, the overall weighted mean score of 2.88 was greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This implies that the librarians' acceptance of metadata mapping and aggregation practices with respect to perceived ease of use construct was high. Also the calculated mean scores of all the four items tested under Perceived usefulness construct are greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50 under 4-point likert scale. However, the overall weighted mean score of 2.83 was greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This implies that the librarians' acceptance of metadata mapping and aggregation practices with respect to perceived usefulness construct was also high.

The table also reveals that the calculated mean scores of all the two items tested under use intention construct are greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50 under 4-point likert scale. However, the overall weighted mean score of 2.69 was greater than the cut-off mean score of 2.50. This implies that the librarians' acceptance of metadata mapping and aggregation practices with respect to use intention construct was high. Moreover, the calculated mean scores of the item tested under decision maker construct (M= 2.80) is greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50 under 4-point likert scale. This implies that the librarians' acceptance of metadata mapping and aggregation practices with respect to decision maker construct was high. This shows the respondents' effort to avoid what has been observed by Weiner (2009) who noted that more than half of all unsuccessful large-scale organisational change efforts are as a result of failure to establish sufficient readiness.

HYPOTHESES TESTING

Table 5: Correlations between librarian’s knowledge level of metadata mapping and aggregation practices and their readiness level to adopt metadata mapping and aggregation for information retrieval.

		Knowledge level	Readiness level
Knowledge level	Pearson Correlation	1	.562
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	402	402
Readiness level	Pearson Correlation	.562	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	402	402

The data on table 5 above showed that there was a very strong positive correlation (relationship) between librarians’ knowledge of metadata mapping and aggregation and their readiness level to adopt metadata mapping and aggregation for information retrieval, which was statistically significant ($r = .562$, $n = 402$, $p = .000$, i.e less than 0.05) therefore, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate hypothesis since $p < .05$. This implies that there is a statistically significant relationship between the librarian’s knowledge of metadata mapping and aggregation practices and their readiness level to adopt metadata mapping and aggregation for information retrieval.

Table 6 Correlations between the librarians’ knowledge of metadata mapping and aggregation practices and the extent to which they accept metadata mapping and aggregation practices in their libraries

		Knowledge level	Acceptance level
Knowledge level	Pearson Correlation	1	.245
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	402	402
Acceptance level	Pearson Correlation	.245	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	402	402

The data in Table 6 above showed that there was a weak positive correlation (relationship) between librarians’ knowledge of metadata mapping and aggregation and their acceptance level to adopt metadata mapping and aggregation for information retrieval, which was statistically significant ($r = .245$, $n = 402$, $p = .000$, i.e., less than 0.05). Therefore, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate hypothesis since $p < .05$. This implies that there is a statistically significant relationship between the librarians’ knowledge of metadata mapping and aggregation practices and their readiness level to adopt metadata mapping and aggregation for information retrieval.

With regard to the relationship that exists between the variables, a relationship exists between the librarians’ knowledge level of metadata mapping and aggregation practices and their readiness level to adopt metadata mapping and aggregation for information retrieval, as well as the

librarians' knowledge of metadata mapping and aggregation practices and their acceptance level to adopt metadata mapping and aggregation for information retrieval. These findings justify the submission of Akande and Belle (2014), who emphasized the existence of a relationship between knowledge of an innovation and its adoption, where they remarked that an organization's awareness of a technology is important for the success of implementation. If an organization is aware of a technology, it will be able to make necessary preparations before adoption, and this will increase the success of its implementation. The findings also coincide with the recommendation of Rogers (1995) that before adopting a new innovation, there must be some way in which potential adopters learn or become aware of the innovation. They then form a favorable or unfavorable attitude toward the innovation and accept the innovation, having been convinced of its usefulness and compatibility with their existing values.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The librarians were moderately aware of metadata mapping practices. This finding corroborates the finding of Kaiser et al. (2021) who revealed that librarians exhibit limited awareness of metadata mapping and aggregation, focusing more on creating and analyzing cataloging metadata. The extent to which the librarians accept metadata mapping and aggregation practices was high. This finding coincides with the submission of Darcovich, Flynn, & Li (2018) who reported that librarians' acceptance of metadata mapping and aggregation improved has through collaborative efforts, resulting in enhanced communication and workflows.

The levels at which librarians were ready in terms of training is high, moderate in terms of infrastructure and low in terms of competencies. This finding advocates for compliance with the suggestion made Graser & Burel (2018) that librarians must possess expertise in metadata description, management across multiple schemas, and technical skills like XML, to effectively map and aggregate metadata. This readiness is crucial for adapting to automation and enhancing data quality in library systems. There is a statistically significant relationship between the librarian's knowledge of metadata mapping and aggregation practices and their readiness level to adopt metadata mapping and aggregation for information retrieval. This coincides with the submission of Akande and Belle (2014), who noted the existence of relationship between knowledge of the innovation and its adoption.

There is a statistically significant relationship between the librarian's knowledge of metadata mapping and aggregation practices and their acceptance level to adopt metadata mapping and aggregation for information retrieval. This finding justifies the submission of Dombek & Wallwitz (2016) who emphasized that understanding the technical aspects of metadata mapping is vital for librarians to embrace new data exchange formats.

CONCLUSION

This study aims to shed light on the critical role that librarians' knowledge plays in the adoption of metadata mapping and aggregation for information retrieval in Nigerian federal universities. The influence of librarians' knowledge on the adoption of metadata practices is extremely imperative for the successful implementation of digital library systems in Nigerian federal universities. Exploring the knowledge gaps and their influence on the acceptance of metadata mapping and

aggregation will provide valuable insights for developing targeted training and professional development programs that can enhance librarians' competencies required in facilitating information retrieval. Therefore, this study will contribute to the broader discourse on digital transformation in university libraries by offering practical recommendations for ensuring that librarians are well-equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills that not only will enhance the quality of information retrieval services in federal university libraries but also support the long-term sustainability and promotion of digital libraries in Nigeria at large.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Universities should organize targeted training programs focusing on metadata standards, tools, and best practices. These programs should be continuous and tailored to the specific needs and existing knowledge levels of librarians.
2. Librarians should be encouraged to pursue certifications and continuing education opportunities in metadata management so as to boost their readiness level of its adoption.
3. Library science programs in Nigerian universities should be revised to include comprehensive courses on metadata management, digital cataloging, and information retrieval systems. This will ensure that upcoming librarians accept the innovation with the necessary skills.
4. In addition to theoretical knowledge, practical sessions on using metadata tools and platforms should be included in the curriculum. This hands-on experience will enhance the proficiency of future librarians.
5. Universities should establish forums or platforms where librarians can share best practices, challenges, and solutions related to metadata management initiatives.

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